

Crop establishment with inverted-T seeder

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We compared the newly developed inverted-T seeder (see figure) with traditional sowing methods. Experimental treatments were conventional tillage and hand sowing (one plowing by carabao, two harrowings, seed furrows made with lithao, seed dibbling and covering by hand) (CTH); conventional tillage and

Inverted-T seeder.

Effect of tillage and sowing methods on upland crop establishment. IRRI.

Tillage and sowing method	Plant emergence ^a (%)		
	Maize	Soybean	Mungbean
Conventional tillage and hand sowing	41 b (49)	29 b (39)	15 b (15)
Conventional tillage and seeder sowing	67 a (77)	24 b (46)	49 a (65)
No-till and seeder sowing	69 a (73)	45 a (58)	46 a (56)

^a Seed germination = maize 97%, soybean 47% and mungbean 75%. Values in parentheses indicate plant emergence, including subsurface surviving seedlings, at 12 d after sowing. In each column, values followed by different letters show significant differences at P 0.05.

inverted-T seeder-sown (CTI); and no-tillage and inverted-T seeder sown (NTI).

Mean soil moisture potential at seeding was -11 kPa for CTH, -14 kPa for CTI, and -19 kPa for NTI. Each tillage treatment area was divided into three 20- × 3.5-m plots with 0.3-m row spacing. They were sown with maize at 5 seeds/m row, soybean at 7 seeds/m row, or mungbean at 18 seeds/m row.

Soil was sandy clay loam in an upland field previously under sorghum. Glyphosate herbicide at 4 liters/ha was sprayed to control sorghum ratoons and other weeds in no-till plots. Plant establishment counts represented 25% of total planted area.

Plant establishment with the

inverted-T seeder (average of CTI and NTI) was 65% better in maize and 300% better in mungbean than with CTH (see table).

Analysis of the unemerged seed recovered suggested that a large proportion of seed did not germinate in CTH. In-groove soil studies suggested that uneven depth of seed placement and low bulk density in CTH plots resulted in low soil moisture conduction (particularly capillary) from the soil matrix and low availability at the seed interface. More subsurface surviving seedlings were found in both CTI and NTI plots, suggesting further potential plant establishment if more moisture had been available. □

Effect of green manure on yield

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We studied the effects of azolla and sunhemp incorporation with eight treatments in a randomized block design replicated four times during summer 1986. Soil was red sandy loam (Alfisol) with pH 7.4, 1.2% organic matter, 15 kg available Olsen's P/ha, and 146 kg available K/ha. Azolla *A. pinnata* with 4.7% N and 0.3% P, and sunhemp *Crotalaria juncea* at 2.5% N and 0.2% P were incorporated 3 wk before transplanting.

Effect of green manure on nutrient uptake and rice yield at Karnataka, India.

Treatment ^a	Uptake (kg/ha) (grain and straw)		Recovery (%) (grain and straw)		Grain yield (t/ha)
	N	P	N	P	
Azolla at 100 kg N/ha, basal	79.2	14.0	20.9	26.8	5.1
Azolla at 50 kg N/ha + urea in 2 splits at 50 kg N/ha	96.1	16.2	37.8	36.8	5.8
Sunhemp at 100 kg N/ha, basal	75.4	14.1	17.1	27.3	4.9
Sunhemp at 50 kg N/ha + urea in 2 splits at 50 kg N/ha	102.3	16.8	44.0	39.5	6.1
Urea in 3 splits at 100 kg N/ha	77.3	14.3	19.0	28.2	5.2
Sunhemp at 25 kg N/ha + urea at 50 kg N/ha	80.2	10.2	29.2	9.5	5.0
Urea at 75 kg N/ha	70.1	12.2	15.7	18.6	4.4
Control, no N	58.3	8.1	—	—	2.6
'F' Test	**				**
CD (0.01)	9.8				0.5
CV (%)	3.2				8.7

^a All treatments received 22 kg P and 41.5 kg K/ha.

Combined green manure and urea to supply equal quantities of recommended N dose yielded

significantly more than urea applied in three splits (see table). □